

A Note on Graded Granular Rough Sets

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Abstract. Of the many generalizations of rough sets in the literature, graded rough sets are among the most controversial. When approached from a pointwise perspective, these are closely related to graded modal logic. In this research, a few granular generalizations are proposed by the present author. Some mistakes in the literature are rectified and definable operations are examined by her. These are also relevant to the semantics of variable precision rough sets and generalizations thereof.

Keywords: Graded Rough Sets, Granular Rough Sets, Rough Mereology, VPRS, Algebraic Semantics

1 Introduction

The literature on variable precision rough sets [1,2] and generalizations (including hybrid variants thereof) has been mostly focused on applications. Of the limited theoretical results, it is known that graded rough sets are closely related to it. But the latter is studied in a very few papers alone.

In graded rough sets, approximations are constructed relative to integral grades that are related to the cardinality of sets. The granulation is assumed to be the set of arbitrary neighborhoods generated by points in [3] and the approximations are defined pointwise. They are not always granular in the sense of the present author [4,5,6]. Granular approximations generated by equivalence relations are studied in [7] (though the definition used is different from [3], they coincide). Here this will be generalized to arbitrary granulations (to an extent) and examined. While these can be related to variable precision rough sets in some cases, they can be also suggestive of the use of mutually inconsistent procedures in their construction. A number of incorrect claims in [7] are also

pointed out, and parts of a new algebraic semantics is proposed by the present author.

The reader is expected to be familiar with the axiomatic approach to granularity due to the present author in [4,5], and the concept of granularity is uniformly used in that sense.

2 Graded Rough Sets

A *grade* k can be any positive integer, and is related to the cardinality of granules or sets used in the context. Let S be a collection of sets (that are subsets of a H), and \mathcal{G} be the set of neighborhoods generated by a neighborhood map $n : H \mapsto \wp H$. The version of graded rough sets explored in [3] is based on the following k -approximation operators and derived quantities (for any $A \in \wp(H) = S$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^{u_k} &= \{z : n(z) \in \mathcal{G} \ \& \ \#(n(z) \cap A) > k\} && \text{(k-upper1)} \\
 A^{l_k} &= \{z : n(z) \in \mathcal{G} \ \& \ \#(n(z) \setminus A) \leq k\} && \text{(k-lower1)} \\
 \text{Pos}_k^p(A) &= A^{u_k} \cap A^{l_k} && \text{(k-positive region1)} \\
 \text{Neg}_k^p(A) &= H \setminus (A^{l_k} \cup A^{u_k}) && \text{(k-negative region1)} \\
 \text{Bnd}_{u_k}^p(A) &= A^{u_k} \setminus A^{l_k} && \text{(upper k-boundary1)} \\
 \text{Bnd}_{l_k}^p(A) &= A^{l_k} \setminus A^{u_k} && \text{(lower k-boundary1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

A^{l_k} is the pointwise k -lower approximation of A , while the pointwise k -upper approximation is A^{u_k} .

It is obvious that even if \mathcal{G} is a partition, it can happen that $A^{l_k} \not\subseteq A$ and $A \not\subseteq A^{u_k}$. For this reason alone, it is not a very rational kind of approximation. Further the construction presupposes complete knowledge of the context or domain (with no scope for vagueness). Semantic duality results have limited scope in the situation. The approximation operators are graded modal operators though, and satisfy the following properties [3]:

Proposition 1. *In the above context,*

$$\begin{aligned}
A^{l^p} &= A^{l_0^p} & (\text{GL0}) \\
A^{l_k^p} &= \neg((\neg A)^{u_k^p}) & (\text{GL1}) \\
H^{l_k^p} &= H & (\text{GL2}) \\
(A \cap B)^{l_k^p} &\subseteq A^{l_k^p} \cap B^{l_k^p} & (\text{GL3}) \\
A^{l_k^p} \cup B^{l_k^p} &\subseteq (A \cup B)^{l_k^p} & (\text{GL4}) \\
A \subseteq B &\longrightarrow A^{l_k^p} \subseteq B^{l_k^p} & (\text{GL5}) \\
k \leq t &\longrightarrow A^{l_k^p} \subseteq A^{l_t^p} & (\text{GL6}) \\
A^{u_0^p} &= A^{u^p} & (\text{GU0}) \\
A^{u_k^p} &= \neg((\neg A)^{l_k^p}) & (\text{GU1}) \\
\emptyset^{u_k^p} &= \emptyset & (\text{GU2}) \\
A^{u_k^p} \cup B^{u_k^p} &\subseteq (A \cup B)^{u_k^p} & (\text{GU3}) \\
(A \cap B)^{u_k^p} &\subseteq A^{u_k^p} \cap B^{u_k^p} & (\text{GU4}) \\
A \subseteq B &\longrightarrow A^{u_k^p} \subseteq B^{u_k^p} & (\text{GU5}) \\
k \leq t &\longrightarrow A^{u_t^p} \cap A^{u_k^p} & (\text{GU6})
\end{aligned}$$

This makes it a graded modal logic of a form. Semantics of graded modal logics (see [8,9] and related references) and their limitations are applicable to this non-granular approach. When R is an equivalence, the additional modal axioms satisfied are:

$$\begin{aligned}
A^{l_0^p} &\subseteq A^{u_0^p} & (\text{GD}) \\
A^{l_0^p} &\subseteq A & (\text{GT}) \\
A &\subseteq (A^{u_0^p})^{l_0^p} & (\text{GB}) \\
A^{l_k^p} &\subseteq (A^{l_k^p})^{l_0^p} & (\text{G4}) \\
A^{u_k^p} &\subseteq (A^{u_k^p})^{l_0^p} & (\text{G5})
\end{aligned}$$

3 Granular Generalizations

A *grade* k (as before) can be any positive integer, and is related to the cardinality of granules or sets used in the context. Let S be a collection of sets (that are subsets of a H), and \mathcal{G} a subset of S .

Definition 1. *If k is a fixed positive integer and $x \in S$, then the k -lower and k -upper approximations and related regions will be*

$$\begin{aligned} x^{u_k} &= \bigcup \{h : h \in \mathcal{G} \ \& \ \#(h \cap x) > k\} && \text{(k-upper)} \\ x^{l_k} &= \bigcup \{h : h \in \mathcal{G} \ \& \ \#(h) - \#(h \cap x) \leq k\} && \text{(k-lower)} \\ \text{Pos}_k(x) &= x^{u_k} \cap x^{l_k} && \text{(k-positive region)} \\ \text{Neg}_k(x) &= H \setminus (x^{l_k} \cup x^{u_k}) && \text{(k-negative region)} \\ \text{Bnd}_k^u(x) &= x^{u_k} \setminus x^{l_k} && \text{(upper k-boundary)} \\ \text{Bnd}_k^l(x) &= x^{l_k} \setminus x^{u_k} && \text{(lower k-boundary)} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2. *Two elements $x, w \in S$ will be*

- k -lower roughly equal (in symbols, $x \approx_{l_k} w$) if and only if $x^{l_k} = w^{l_k}$,
- k -upper roughly equal (in symbols, $x \approx_{u_k} w$) if and only if $x^{u_k} = w^{u_k}$,
- k -roughly equal (in symbols, $x \approx_k w$) if and only if $x^{l_k} = w^{l_k}$ and $x^{u_k} = w^{u_k}$.

Proposition 2. *The range of the operations u_k and l_k on $\wp(H)$ need not be equal even when \mathcal{G} is a partition of H , and $S = \wp(S)$.*

Proof. The range of definition of the operations u_k and l_k are subsets of the set of all unions of neighborhood granules. Suppose these are H_{u_k} and H_{l_k} . Counterexamples for showing the inequality of the two can be based on the following general considerations:

If $[z]$ is an equivalence class (with $z \in H$) with less than or equal to k elements, then it's k -lower approximation is $[z]$, but its k -upper approximation would be the empty set. In fact, $[z] \notin H_{u_k}$ will hold (and neither will a super-set of $[z]$ be in H_{u_k}). If $[z]$ is an equivalence class with more than k elements, then it will be in both H_{l_k} and H_{u_k} . So it can happen that $H_{l_k} \neq H_{u_k}$.

It is known that [7]

Theorem 1. *When $H = \bigcup S = \bigcup \mathcal{G}$, and \mathcal{G} is a collection of disjoint sets (that is a partition), then*

$$\text{Bnd}_k^l x = \emptyset \leftrightarrow x^{l_k} \subseteq x^{u_k} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Bnd}_k^u x = \emptyset \leftrightarrow x^{u_k} \subseteq x^{l_k} \quad (2)$$

$$x^{u_k u_k} = x^{u_k} \subseteq x^{u_k l_k} \quad (3)$$

$$x^{u_k l_k} = x^{u_k} \cup \{\cup\{h : h \in \mathcal{G} \ \& \ \#(h) \leq k\}\} \quad (4)$$

$$x^{l_k u_k} \subseteq x^{l_k} = x^{l_k l_k} \quad (5)$$

$$x^{l_k} = (x^{l_k})^{u_k} \cup \{\cup\{h : h \in \mathcal{G} \ \& \ \#(h) \leq k\}\} \quad (6)$$

Concepts of outer and inner boundaries are defined as follows

$$\text{Bnd}_k^{\text{ou}}(a, b) = \cup\{h : h \subseteq a^{u_k}, \ \& \ h \subseteq b^{u_k} \ \& \ h \not\subseteq (a \cup b)^{u_k}\} \\ \text{(o-u k-boundary)}$$

$$\text{Bnd}_k^{\text{ol}}(a, b) = \cup\{h : h \subseteq a^{l_k}, \ \& \ h \subseteq b^{l_k} \ \& \ h \not\subseteq (a \cup b)^{l_k}\} \\ \text{(o-l k-boundary)}$$

$$\text{Bnd}_k^{\text{i u}}(a, b) = \cup\{h : h \not\subseteq a^{u_k}, \ \& \ h \not\subseteq b^{u_k} \ \& \ h \subseteq (a \cup b)^{u_k}\} \\ \text{(i-u k-boundary)}$$

$$\text{Bnd}_k^{\text{il}}(a, b) = \cup\{h : h \not\subseteq a^{l_k}, \ \& \ h \not\subseteq b^{l_k} \ \& \ h \subseteq (a \cup b)^{l_k}\} \\ \text{(i-l k-boundary)}$$

Erroneous claims (Definition 4 and beyond) are made in [7] in relation to definable operations on the power set ($\wp(H)$). The authors claim that $\underline{\text{cup}}$, $\overline{\cap}$, and \sim^* are total operations and that the graded approximations are epimorphisms, but in their formulation these are wrong and ill-defined. In fact, similar mistakes are repeated for VPRS. *For example, the following definition is improper as z and w can be written as k -upper approximations in multiple ways to yield different results:* For any $z, w \in \wp(H)$, if $z = a^{u_k} \ \& \ w = b^{u_k}$, then $z \sqcup w := a^{u_k} \cup b^{u_k} \cup \text{Bnd}_k^{\text{i u}}(a, b)$.

The mistakes are not resolvable from [7]. So the following new definitions are introduced by the present author:

Definition 3. For any $a, b \in \wp(H)$

$$\begin{aligned}
a \sqcup_u b &:= a^{u_k} \cup b^{u_k} \cup \text{Bnd}_k^{iu}(a, b) && (\text{sqcup}_u) \\
a \sqcup_l b &:= a^{l_k} \cup b^{l_k} \cup \text{Bnd}_k^{il}(a, b) && (\text{sqcup}_l) \\
a \sqcap_u b &:= (a^{u_k} \cap b^{u_k}) \setminus \text{Bnd}_k^{ou}(a, b) && (\text{sqcap}_u) \\
a \sqcap_l b &:= (a^{l_k} \cap b^{l_k}) \setminus \text{Bnd}_k^{ol}(a, b) && (\text{sqcap}_l) \\
\neg_u a &= (a^{u_k})^c && (\neg_u) \\
\neg_l a &= (a^{l_k})^c && (\neg_l)
\end{aligned}$$

Further, if c denotes complementation in $\wp(H)$, then for any $z \in \wp(H)$

$$\neg z := \begin{cases} (a^{u_k})^c & \text{if } z = a^{u_k} \\ (a^{l_k})^c & \text{if } z = a^{l_k} \\ \text{undefined otherwise} & \end{cases} \quad (\neg)$$

Theorem 2. The partial/total operations of Def 3 are well-defined on $\wp(H)$.

Proof. It is obvious that $\sqcup_u, \sqcup_l, \sqcap_u, \sqcap_l, \neg_l$ and \neg_u are all well-defined as their evaluation can be done in only one way. Also if $z = a^{u_k} = b^{l_k}$ for some $a, b, z \in \wp(H)$, then the evaluation of $\neg z$ remains unique.

The defined operations satisfy the following properties

Theorem 3. • $\sqcup_l, \sqcup_u, \sqcap_l$ and \sqcap_u are all commutative, idempotent operations.

- $\sqcup_l, \sqcup_u, \sqcap_l$ and \sqcap_u are not necessarily associative.
- For any $a, b \in \wp(H)$, $a \sqcup_u b = (a \cup b)^{u_k}$
- For any $a, b \in \wp(H)$, $a \sqcap_l b = (a \cap b)^{l_k}$
- For any $a, b \in \wp(H)$, $a \sqcup_l b = (a \cup b)^{l_k}$
- For any $a, b \in \wp(H)$, $a \sqcap_u b = (a \cap b)^{u_k}$

Proof. All the claims can be directly verified.

3.1 k-Rough Objects

It is possible to define a number of ideas of roughly equal objects in the context of graded rough sets. These can be done in relation to a fixed k or in relation to a number of possible values of k .

Definition 4. *In the context of definition 1, by a k-lower rough object will be meant a maximal set (with respect to set inclusion) of mutually k-lower equal elements of S. Similarly, a k-upper rough object will be a maximal set (with respect to set inclusion) of mutually k-upper equal elements of S. Further a k-rough object will be a maximal set of mutually k-roughly equal elements of S.*

Equivalently, they can be defined as equivalence classes of k-lower roughly equal objects (respectively k-upper and k-roughly equal objects) on $\wp(H)$.

Remarks

Further granular generalizations are possible through generalized rough inclusion functions [10,11,12,13]. But, even in the situation generated by equivalence relations (on a set in the classical semantic domain) the concepts of theoretical aggregation and commonalities work in independent limited ways. This suggests that alternative approaches should be considered for modeling the k-rough objects.

Applications including hybrid ones of VPRS motivate further study of possible generalizations. These are also motivated by forthcoming research due to the present author on rationality in the general rough set and clustering contexts, that extend the work in [14].

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References

1. Ziarko, W.: Variable Precision Rough Set Model. *J. of Computer and System Sciences* **46** (1993) 39–59
2. Katzberg, T., Ziarko, W.: Variable Precision Extension of Rough Sets. *Fundamenta Informaticae* **27** (1996) 1–12
3. Yao, Y.Y., Lin, T.Y.: Generalizing Rough Sets Using Modal Logics. *Intelligent Automation and Soft Computing* **2**(2) (1996) 103–120
4. Mani, A.: Comparative Approaches to Granularity in General Rough Sets. In Bello, R., et al., eds.: *IJCRS 2020*. Volume 12179 of *LNAI*. Springer (2020) 500–518
5. Mani, A.: Algebraic Methods for Granular Rough Sets. In Mani, A., Düntsch, I., Cattaneo, G., eds.: *Algebraic Methods in General Rough Sets*. Trends in Mathematics. Birkhauser Basel (2018) 157–336

6. Mani, A.: Dialectics of Counting and The Mathematics of Vagueness. *Transactions on Rough Sets XV*(LNCS 7255) (2012) 122–180
7. Zhang, X., Mo, Z., Xiong, F., Cheng, W.: Comparative Study of Variable Precision Rough Set Model and Graded Rough Set Model. *Internat. J. Appr. Reasoning* **53** (2012) 104–116
8. Chen, J., van Ditmarsch, H., Greco, G., Tzimoulis, A.: Neighbourhood Semantics for Graded Modal Logic. *ArXiv* **2105.09202** (2021) 1–12
9. de Rijke, M.: A Note on Graded Modal Logic. *Studia Logica* **64**(2) (2000) 271–283
10. Mani, A.: Algebraic Semantics of Generalized RIFs. *ArXiv Preprint* (2109.12998) (2021) 1–36
11. Mani, A.: High Granular Operator Spaces and Less-Contaminated General Rough Mereologies. *Forthcoming* (2019) 1–77
12. Gomolinska, A.: Rough Approximation Based on Weak q -RIFs. *Transactions on Rough Sets X* (2009) 117–135
13. Gomolinska, A.: On Certain Rough Inclusion Functions. In Peters, J.F., et al., eds.: *Transactions on Rough Sets IX*, LNCS 5390. Springer Verlag (2008) 35–55
14. Mani, A.: General Rough Modeling of Cluster Analysis. In Ramanna, S., et al., eds.: *Rough Sets: IJCRS-EUSFLAT 2021*. LNAI 12872. Springer Nature (2021)